

THE PLACE AND TYPES OF THE TERM CRISIS IN CENTRAL ASIAN HISTORY

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Crisis times are one of the most important parts of human history and are usually explained by the fact that they cause many problems and issues.

We will try to consider some of them in the example of the material of the states that exist in the world and in our history. First of all, let us briefly dwell on the term crisis: Crisis (from ancient Greek –deviation, consequence) aggravation of the situation is reflected in the sense of sudden, sudden change, crisis and dangerous, difficult situation.

In modern usage, the meaning of the term crisis is probably preserved only in the fields of medicine, psychology and economics. A crisis in medicine can mean a sharp worsening of the disease, but then the disease can be cured.

Moreover, a crisis in psychology is a period in which an inevitable but naturally overcome state is possible. Conversely, in

ABSTRACT

This article provides an overview of the types and classifications of crises, and classifies crisis situations that have occurred directly in the history of existing states in the Central Asian region. In particular, the results of the comparison are presented in tables.

relation to economics, politics, or culture, the term crisis is used when it refers to specific negative situations.

We can see in the history of the world's nations that this does not happen immediately, but in the pre-crisis period there was a decline in all parts of those states, and then we saw on the basis of historical events that it became apparent.

Crisis is different and can take on different meanings and different perceptions in each area. Below we will focus on the types and characteristics of crises:

1. The economic crisis:

The economic crisis itself is divided into two types, according to which:

1.1. Financial crisis

1.2. Energy crisis.

The economic crisis is manifested in the imbalance between supply and demand for goods and services. In a competitive

economy through a crisis, there is a mass selection of effective owners.¹ The crisis may renew the ideological, political conditions of the elite and so on.

Karl Marx pointed out that there were no recurring booms and depressions before the Industrial Revolution in the late eighteenth century

Because these cycles appeared on the historical stage at the same time as modern industry, Marx explains that crises are a characteristic of the capitalist economy and not a type of money or credit interest that existed long before capitalism. On the contrary, Marx says that the cause of the crisis is seen in the production of goods that are in high demand.²

2. Socio-Demographic Crisis:

It is about being associated with extinction factors of people due to lack of reproduction. Extinction is a biological and ecological phenomenon in which the extinction of all members of a particular biological species or taxon can lead to "death". The extinction of biological species in a short period of time often speaks of mass extinction.

3. Military-political Crisis:

This is one of the most important types of crisis, which is mainly based on the political crisis. The political crisis is a complex transition period of any social system, which is interrupted in its activity. A crisis is a turning point that can have positive or negative consequences for this system. A situation in which the balance of power in a country or region is disturbed and rivals hope to improve their situation and escalate the conflict can lead to this

¹ Glushchenko V. V. Introduction to crisis science. Financial crisis. Antikrizisnoe upravlenie - M.: IP Glushchenko V. V., 2008, st. 88

² Karl Marx, "Capital," Tom. 1. 1867.

crisis. Examples are Ancient Rome³ and Ancient Greece⁴ We can take as an example the military-political crises in the states.

4. Psychological crisis:

This crisis is often a psychological process associated with the need to change behavior, and is mainly applied to the individual. For example, the onset of such a psychological crisis in the heads of a particular region, country or province is one of the main signs that this region, country or province will eventually disappear from the scene of history.

5. Philosophical crisis:

Acute social change is seen as a philosophical crisis that leads to the disappearance of traditions and the emergence of eschatological myths⁵.

Speaking of eschatology:

Eschatology (Greek e'okhatov, eschaton - "end" logos - "speech", "story", "science") is called, to the fields of theology, physics, philosophy, and futurology devoted to the subject of mankind, civilization, or the end of the world (the end of time). The interpretation of this word explains similar meanings by itself.

6. Migration crises:

Migration (lat. Migratio - I move, I change my place)- 1) the population of a settlement migration from place to place is called Population migration. 2) Migration of animals from one geographical area to another due to changes in habitat

³ Dementeva V.V. 2006: Rimskaya Respublika: Institutsionalnaya istoriya i semiologiya // Politika. Ideology. Culture: Problems of all history: sb. nauch. tr. / V. V. Dementeva, M. E. Erin (ed. Ed.). Yaroslavl, 3-11.

⁴ History of Ancient Greece. // Under red.V.I.Kuzishchina. M.: Vqsshaya shkola, 1996.

⁵ Sidorina T. Yu. "Philosophy of Crisis" M.: Flinta: Nauka, 2003. - 456 s

conditions or development cycle is called Animal migration 3) Displacement of chemical elements in the Earth's crust or surface. Migration of elements. 4) Transfer of energy from one particle to another Energy migration. 5) Regular outflow of capital from one country to another for added value and political purposes. Population migration is the movement of people to change their place of residence, this meaning is of course used in the modern interpretation, and it is useful for us to study the crises associated with the migration of the ancient population. We scientists are well aware that the migration crisis is not a new phenomenon. It is no exaggeration to say that for thousands of years, war, disease, famine, political instability and, of course, forced migration have served millions of refugees and sometimes the disappearance of certain ethnic groups. In this case, the problems that arise through migration do not affect both the migrants and the regions, peoples and countries that receive them. If we think about it, with the right approach, mass migration of the population can lead to the development of new technologies, social processes and the improvement of the gene pool. If migration problems cannot be overcome, they can lead to the collapse of even the most powerful empires, as has happened many times in history.

7. Ecological crisis:

Loss of hemostasis is an important part of ecosystem. It leads to the extinction of some species. May be anthropogenic in nature. I hope it would be a mistake to think one way or another when we say ecological crisis. Why did we criticize the ecological crisis because not only ecological but also the whims of nature have caused

many regions, countries, cities and districts to disappear in ancient times, For example, we have seen in many historical examples that a certain city has shifted due to the change of a river or its tributary, and perhaps you can find traces of an ancient river or sea around the area where you live.

While writing about the above crises, I think it is expedient for us to include a crisis. It is a religious crisis, and as people become more modern and more realistic in their lives, it is natural that the old religion will not be able to fulfill its function. As a result, if there is no question of modernizing religion among the society, there will be a way to renounce this religion. While this serves as an unacceptable process for supporters of one-sided religious dogmatism, it is seen as a situation that complicates daily life for the people and society. The difference between the two serves as one of the causes of the religious crisis⁶. An example of this is Christianity in the sixteenth century, along with the ancient religions. Now that some features of the religion have not completely disappeared, its elements are preserved in temples and pyramids, in rituals, in everyday life. In particular, although the main religion of our time is Islam, we can observe some elements of our old religions. In this article we are considering, all of the crises mentioned above are specific to states and empires, and any of these crises will be observed from the time they arise until the time they fall.

In the table below, I would like to briefly dwell on the role of crises analyzed in the

⁶ Timothy Winter. Islam in the 21st Century (Finding the Qibla in the Postmodern World)

empires and dynastic states that ruled in the history of my country.

As can be seen from the table above, there are many reasons for the crisis of empires, states and dynasties. But it is clear that without a crisis, it will be a military-political crisis. It should be noted that this does not mean that the military-political crisis will happen quickly. There must be many reasons for this to happen.

In conclusion, if we cite 26 countries that have clearly dominated the history of our country, we can see that in almost all of these countries, first of all, the military-political crisis is at the forefront. In 25 countries.

In second place is the economy, which ensures the independence of states, and the countries whose economic sectors have been disrupted accelerate the loss of their

independence, which is the case in the history of 20 countries.

The third is the socio-demographic crisis, which can be seen in 12 countries in the history of our country.

If we look at the psychological crisis in the fourth place, it seems that it happened in 9 countries.

In the fifth place is the number of countries with a philosophical crisis, in the sixth place When we talk about the migration crisis, in all countries and dynasties there were migrations of small and large peoples, sometimes successful, sometimes unsuccessful and in the last place is the environmental crisis, which can only be seen as one of the factors that led to the decline of the Arab caliphate of the dynasty that ruled us.

№	Crisis	Economic crisis	Socio-demographic crisis	Military-political crisis	Psychological crisis	Philosophical crisis	Migrational crisis	Ecological crisis	Natural Crisis
	Empires, states and dynasties								
1	Achaemenid Empire	+		+		+	+	+	+
2	Alexander the Great's empire		+		+		+		+
3	The Seleucid state	+	+	+			+		+
4	Greece - Bactrian Military-political crisis state	+		+			+		+
5	Kushan Empire	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6	The state of Xionid's			+			+		+
7	State of Kidaris		+	+			+		+
8	The state of the Hephthalites	+	+	+	+		+		+
9	Turkish Khanate	+	+	+			+		+
10	Arab Caliphate	+		+		+	+	+	+
11	The Tahirid dynasty			+			+		+
12	The Samanid state	+		+	+		+		+
13	The state of the Karakhanids		+	+		+	+	+	+
14	The state of G'aznavid's	+		+			+		+

15	Seljuk state	+		+			+		+
16	Anushtegin state	+		+			+		+
17	Amir Temur and the Timurid dynasty	+	+	+	+		+		+
18	Bukhara khanate during the Shaybanid dynasty			+	+	+	+	+	+
19	Bukhara khanate during the Ashtarkhanid dynasty	+	+	+			+		+
20	The Emirate of Bukhara during the Mangit dynasty	+		+	+		+		+
21	Khiva khanate during the Shaybanid dynasty	+	+	+			+		+
22	Khiva khanate during the Kungrad dynasty	+		+	+		+		+
23	Kokand khanate	+		+	+		+		+
24	Turkestan Autonomy	+		+		+	+	+	+
25	Bukhara People's Soviet Republic	+	+	+		+	+	+	+
26	Khorezm People's Soviet Republic	+	+	+		+	+	+	+

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5. Sidorina T. Yu. "Philosophy of Crisis" M.: Flinta: Nauka, 2003. - 456 s
6. Timothy Winter. Islam in the 21st Century (Finding the Qibla in the Postmodern World)